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22q11 deletion syndrome, CACNA1A mutations, and sleep deprivation: from theta waves to the cognitive impairments of schizophrenia

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Abstract

Background: Sleep disorders and schizophrenia have a reciprocal relationship: the poorer the sleep quality, the more severe the psychotic symptoms, and conversely, improved sleep quality appears to be associated with an improvement in psychotic symptoms. The physiological mechanisms underlying this interaction are currently unknown.

Objectives: To describe one of the physiological mechanisms underlying this interaction, to see the consequences for cognition and to derive possibilities for therapeutic action.

Methods: We will review three relevant human models for studying the physiology of schizophrenic spectrum disorders: 22q11 deletion syndrome, CACNA1A mutations, and sleep deprivation. We will begin by examining the correlation between sleep quality and the extent of theta waves on resting-state EEG, on the one hand, and symptoms and cognition, on the other. Secondly, we will see the pharmacological arguments suggesting that this correlation does not appear to be due to chance before proposing a physiological explanation: the intrusion of local sleep islands into brain function.

Therapeutic consequences: This correlation between the importance of theta waves in the resting-state EEG of patients on the one hand and their cognitive deficits and symptoms on the other could make it possible to improve the latter by using active substances whose action on neuronal processes is reflected by the reduction of theta waves in the resting-state EEG.

Conclusion: The link between cognitive impairment and increased resting theta waves is partially confirmed by pharmacological evidence, as is the possibility of improving cognitive impairment using active substances that normalize this increase. If it were fully confirmed by

35 appropriate clinical trials, this would open up new perspectives for changing the management
36 of schizophrenia spectrum disorders.

37 ---

38 **Introduction :**

39 The incidence and prevalence of schizophrenia spectrum disorders are very high¹ and
40 increasing². Despite all the efforts made in this area, the prognosis for these disorders remains
41 extremely poor^{3,4}. Excess mortality among patients is considerable, whether related to the
42 psychiatric condition itself or not^{5, 6}. Patient's quality of life, employment rates⁷, and marital
43 status⁸ remain extremely poor. Beyond the considerable economic burden this entails^{2, 9, 10, 11}
44 this statistical reality is associated with an infinite number of human, personal and family
45 tragedies.

46 **Sleep disorders and schizophrenia:**

47 The prevalence of sleep disorders in these patients is extremely high: 58% in high-income
48 countries and 89.9% in low-income countries, according to a recent meta-analysis¹². The
49 disorders identified are diverse but all affect sleep quality and its restorative function: shorter
50 total sleep time, longer sleep onset latency, more wake time after sleep onset, lower sleep
51 efficiency, decreased slow-wave sleep (SWS), changes in the duration and latency of REM
52 sleep, and spindle deficits.

53 These disturbances are present from the first psychotic episode¹³ and persist throughout the
54 course of the illness. They are also found in the prodromal phase¹⁴ and in patients at ultra-high
55 risk of psychosis—a group in which their severity is correlated with the risk of transition^{15, 16}.
56 This poor sleep quality corresponds both to the severity of symptoms^{17, 18, 19} both positive²⁰
57 and negative²¹ and to cognitive impairments²². This association between sleep disturbances
58 and psychotic symptoms is not unique to psychosis, as it is also found in the general
59 population^{23, 24, 25, 26}.

60 Conversely, the improvement of sleep disorders seems to go hand in hand with that of
61 psychotic symptoms^{27, 28}, although studies are few in this area²⁹.

62 The bidirectional link between sleep disorders and psychotic symptoms is well established,
63 but the physiological mechanism that connects those remains mysterious³⁰. A study involving
64 a large cohort of twins showed the presence of both a genetic and an environmental
65 component in this relationship³¹, but research aimed at elucidating the genetic mechanisms at
66 work has not yet yielded any conclusive findings^{32, 33}.

67 The aim of our study is to describe one of the physiological mechanisms underlying this
68 interaction, to examine its consequences on cognition, and to identify potential therapeutic
69 applications. To achieve this, we will review three human models, exploring one of the
70 mechanisms linking sleep and cognition.

71

72 **Cognitive disorders and schizophrenia spectrum disorders:**

73 The prevalence of cognitive impairment is extremely high in psychosis disorder, around 80%,
74 and is already present in the prodromal stages³⁴. These impairments exist regardless of the
75 patients' intellectual level³⁵. They are found in both unmedicated³⁶ and chronically ill patients
76 and are stable over time³⁷. Processing speed, verbal memory, working memory, and social
77 cognition are the most affected. Furthermore, these impairments are predictive of patients'
78 outcomes, independent of the symptoms they present³⁸, because cognitive difficulties are
79 predictive of social functioning^{39, 40}.

80 Antipsychotics, the cornerstone of current schizophrenia treatment, do not improve patients'
81 cognitive functioning⁴¹, and of all the active substances tested, only xanomeline showed some
82 effect^{42, 43}. From a non-pharmacological perspective, cognitive remediation slightly improves
83 patients' cognitive impairments and social functioning⁴⁴.

84 Although not included in the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria, cognitive deficits appear to play a
85 central role in the range of disorders associated with schizophrenia⁴⁵. They are not specific to
86 this condition, as the same deficits—albeit significantly less pronounced—are also found in
87 bipolar disorder⁴⁶.

88 The genetic component of these cognitive disorders is certain, but the contribution to risk of
89 the specific alleles identified is extremely modest⁴⁷ and the polygenic risk scores of
90 schizophrenia only marginally overlap with those of cognitive disorders⁴⁸.

91 The environmental component of these cognitive impairments is partly linked to childhood
92 trauma. This observation is not unique to psychotic patients; it is also found in the general
93 population^{49, 50}. These impairments are not necessarily permanent: they can regress in patients
94 with Ultrahigh Risk for Psychosis when their condition improves⁵¹.

95 The physiological mechanisms that link these cognitive disorders to poor sleep quality remain
96 unknown, and the heterogeneity of studies in this area has not allowed them to be specified⁵².

97 To decipher one of these mechanisms, we will review sleep disorders, cognitive impairments,
98 and the variation in the importance of EEG theta waves at rest and during tasks in three
99 human models: 22q11 deletion syndrome, mutations of CACNA1A, and sleep deprivation.
100 We will then examine the pharmacological evidence that indicate this correlation is not due to
101 chance.

102 Finally, we will propose a physiological hypothesis to link clinical disorders and the
103 importance of theta waves: the disruption of brain function caused by local sleep islands, a
104 mechanism reflected by the importance of theta waves of the waking EEG.

105 The use of these three human models is relevant because they share – in addition to sleep
106 disturbances, cognitive impairments, and the increased prominence of resting theta waves
107 reviewed here – physiological characteristics that are implicated in the physiology of
108 schizophrenia:

- 109 - Cerebellar damage which known to be important in schizophrenia spectrum
110 disorders⁵³, ⁵⁴. The 22q11 deletion is accompanied by cerebellar atrophy⁵⁵,
111 CACNA1A mutations cause cerebellar ataxia⁵⁶, and sleep deprivation leads to a
112 significant reduction in in functional connectivity between the cortex and the
113 cerebellum⁵⁷ before leading, if prolonged, to the destruction of Purkinje cells and
114 neurons in the frontal cortex⁵⁸. Modulation of the expression of the Grin2c gene
115 encoding the GluN2C subunit of the NMDA receptor at the level of cerebellar granule
116 cells is a possible link between sleep deprivation-induced cognitive disorders and the
117 cerebellum⁵⁹.
- 118 - A mitochondrial dysfunction known to be linked to the genetics and etiology of
119 schizophrenia spectrum disorders⁶⁰. This dysfunction has been found in 22q11
120 deletion⁶¹, in developmental disorders caused by CACNA1A mutations⁶², and in sleep
121 deprivation⁶³.
- 122 - An alteration in brain connectivity known to be important in schizophrenia spectrum
123 disorders⁶⁴. This alteration is found in 22q11 deletion⁶⁵, in CACNA1A mutations⁶⁶
124 and in sleep deprivation⁶⁷.
- 125 - An alteration in the excitation/inhibition balance, known to be important in
126 schizophrenia spectrum disorders⁶⁸. This alteration is found in an animal model of
127 22q11 deletion⁶⁹, in a neuronal model of CACNA1A haploinsufficiency⁷⁰ and in sleep
128 deprivation⁷¹.

129 It was decided to focus here on spectral EEG power density because it has been studied for a
130 long time and the data in this area are both more numerous and easier to compare than other
131 EEG characteristics such as event-related potentials, connectivity, aperiodic activity, or
132 microstates. Furthermore, theta wave power density reflects various neuronal processes
133 involving cognition and is particularly closely linked to mismatch negativity, a well-validated
134 biomarker in schizophrenia⁷².

135 **22q11 deletion syndrome:**

136 The 22q11 deletion is relatively common: its incidence is estimated at 1 in 2,000 to 4,000 live
137 births. It is associated with an extremely high prevalence and incidence of psychotic
138 disorders, particularly schizophrenia spectrum disorders⁷³. This increased risk of psychosis
139 and the fact that the haplotype involves genes implicated in dopamine regulation make this
140 deletion a relevant model for studying the physiology of psychoses and explain why it has
141 been extensively studied.

142 Cognitive impairment is extremely common in this syndrome⁷⁴, and the severity of this
143 impairment is both correlated with and predictive of the psychotic transition⁷⁵, ⁷⁶. The
144 intensity of the cognitive deficit appears to be linked to that of the negative symptoms⁷⁷. This
145 cognitive impairment leads to disturbances in overall functioning similar to those seen in
146 schizophrenic patients⁷⁸.

147 Very poor sleep quality is also common in this syndrome⁷⁹, ⁸⁰. The decrease in delta waves
148 during NREM sleep reflects poorly restorative sleep, leading to daytime sleepiness due to
149 increased sleep pressure. This is reflected in the morning resting-state EEG by a greater

150 prominence of theta waves⁷⁹. Mice with a similar deletion also exhibit an increase in theta
151 waves on their waking EEG⁸¹.

152 This increase in the importance of theta waves at rest is accompanied by a decrease in their
153 importance during a visual task⁸².

154 **Mutations of CACNA1A:**

155 Mutations in the CACNA1A gene lead to neurological, psychiatric, and cognitive disorders⁸³,
156 ⁶⁶. This gene encodes both the transcription factor α 1ACT, which plays a key role in the
157 development of Purkinje cells, and the pore-forming α 1A subunit, one of the subunits of
158 Cav2.1, also called the P / Q. voltage-dependent calcium channel⁶⁶.

159 Psychiatric disorders associated with these mutations are frequent (34.5%) and their spectrum
160 is broad: anxiety, depression, adjustment disorder, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder,
161 personality disorder, schizophrenia⁶⁶. Cognitive disorders are even more frequent⁶⁶ and mainly
162 concern the following areas: figural memory, visuoconstructive abilities, and verbal fluency⁸³.

163 The Cav2.1 calcium channel plays a very important role in wakefulness⁸⁴ and this role could
164 be partly due to its influence on A1 adenosine receptors⁸⁵.

165 Mutations of CACNA1A therefore logically lead to a significant increase in theta waves of
166 the resting-state EEG⁸⁶, ⁶⁶.

167 **Sleep deprivation:**

168 Sleep deprivation has long been known to lead to cognitive, psychological, and psychiatric
169 disorders.

170 Cognitive impairments are among the first to appear; they affect the three core components of
171 executive functions: working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility⁸⁷. This
172 effect is all the more pronounced the longer the sleep deprivation lasts⁸⁸.

173 The effects on mood are as pronounced as the cognitive impairments⁸⁹: reduced positive
174 affect, increased anxiety symptoms, blunted arousal in response to emotional stimuli,
175 increased negative affects, depression⁹⁰.

176 The longer the sleep deprivation continues, the more serious its psychiatric consequences
177 become: "Perceptual distortions, anxiety, irritability, depersonalization, and temporal
178 disorientation started within 24-48 h of sleep loss, followed by complex hallucinations and
179 disordered thinking after 48-90 h, and delusions after 72 h, after which time the clinical
180 picture resembles that of acute psychosis or toxic delirium. By the third day without sleep,
181 hallucinations in all three sensory modalities were reported"⁹¹.

182 The effects of chronic sleep deprivation are also proven on cognition⁹², ⁹³ emotions⁹⁰ and the
183 onset of psychiatric disorders²⁰.

184 Sleep deprivation, and the resulting sleep pressure, is reflected on an electro-physiological
185 level by an increase in the importance of theta waves in the resting-state EEG⁹⁴; in cases of
186 chronic sleep deprivation, frontal regions are affected more rapidly than parietal regions⁹⁵.

187 There is a significant inter-individual difference in vulnerability to sleep deprivation⁹⁶. This
188 vulnerability is a stable trait for a given individual⁹⁷, and vulnerable individuals are
189 susceptible to both acute and chronic sleep deprivation⁹⁸. This vulnerability manifests as a
190 greater increase in resting theta waves during sleep deprivation, but also at rest in the absence
191 of any sleep deprivation^{99, 100}.

192 It is interesting to note that in these three human models, a high degree of phenotypic
193 variability is observed for the same genetic makeup. The partial discordance of monozygotic
194 twins regarding vulnerability to sleep deprivation rules out the simplest explanation for this
195 phenomenon—the sharing of other vulnerability genes¹⁰¹—as insufficient, since it fails to
196 account for this discordance. This phenotypic variability is also present in the case of
197 schizophrenia in monozygotic twins.

198 **Theta waves at rest and during tasks:**

199 The increased theta waves on resting-state EEG that we observed in the three human models
200 reviewed is also a characteristic feature of the EEG of schizophrenic patients, whether they
201 are medicated or not¹⁰², a feature further correlated with the severity of their cognitive
202 impairment¹⁰³. This increase in resting-state theta waves is accompanied in these patients by a
203 decrease during tasks^{104, 105} or ERPs^{72, 103}. It is observed even in the prodromal stages of the
204 illness¹⁰⁶.

205 Theta waves are often considered a simple reflection of a thalamocortical loop, whereas they
206 appear to reflect multiple physiological mechanisms. For example, their increase on resting-
207 state EEG in children and adolescents is correlated with poor cognitive abilities, while their
208 increase during a task is correlated with good cognitive abilities¹⁰⁷. The importance of theta
209 waves is a reliable indicator of sleep pressure, but their topography does not specifically
210 correspond to that of the brain regions activated during tasks performed in a sleep-deprived
211 state¹⁰⁸. Furthermore, caffeine decreases the importance of theta waves at rest or during sleep
212 deprivation but does not change the importance of theta waves during a task^{109, 110}. Therefore,
213 the increase in theta waves cannot be considered solely as a reflection of a single mechanism
214 of adaptation to a particular situation (task, sleep pressure, mindwandering, etc.).

215 **Cognition, negative symptoms and the importance of theta waves: coincidence or strong** 216 **correlation?**

217 Several active substances that reduce the importance of theta waves on resting-state EEG
218 appear to be effective in improving psychotic symptoms and cognitive disorders in both
219 animals and humans.

220 Thus, 5HT2a receptor agonists, which cause a decrease in theta waves^{111, 112} have shown their
221 ability to counteract in animals the deleterious effects of phencyclidine^{113, 114}, a drug that
222 increases the importance of theta waves¹¹⁵. Similar results were obtained regarding the

223 deleterious effects of ketamine¹¹⁴. This action of 5HT2a receptor agonists can be explained by
224 their presence on glutamatergic neurons¹¹⁶ and their coupled function^{117, 118}.

225 Psychostimulants, such as methylphenidate or dextroamphetamine, which promote
226 wakefulness and lead to a decrease in the importance of resting theta waves in healthy
227 volunteers¹¹⁹ and in pathologies where they are increased (ADHD¹²⁰, Alzheimer's disease¹²¹),
228 have also allowed, at low doses, an improvement in cognitive disorders in schizophrenic
229 patients – whether they have ADHD^{122, 123} or not¹²⁴.

230 Inversely, early treatment of patients with ADHD (before the age of 13) appears to decrease
231 the risk of the onset of non-affective psychosis in this at-risk population¹²⁵.

232 Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors do not exhibit a uniform spectral response on resting-
233 state EEG during major depression: some cause a decrease in theta waves (sertraline,
234 paroxetine, vortioxetine), while others increase them (fluoxetine, citalopram)¹²⁶.

235 Sertraline, which causes a decrease in theta waves on the resting-state EEG, has been the
236 subject of large randomized clinical trials in schizophrenic patients. Combining sertraline with
237 half-dose neuroleptic medication has proven more effective than standard-dose neuroleptic
238 treatment in various contexts, impacting both symptoms and psychosocial functioning: during
239 a first psychotic episode in previously unmedicated patients^{127, 128, 129, 130} and during
240 exacerbations in treatment resistant patients^{131, 132}.

241 Inversely, citalopram which causes an increase in theta waves on the resting-state EEG has
242 not shown any cognitive benefit or improvement in quality of life in schizophrenic patients in
243 two small trials^{133, 134}.

244 Xanomeline, which improves the cognitive abilities of the most severely impaired
245 schizophrenic patients⁴², also leads to a reduction in the importance of theta waves on resting-
246 state EEG in non-human primates¹³⁵ and in aged mice without pathologies¹³⁶.

247 The effectiveness on cognition and symptoms of active substances leading to a decrease in the
248 importance of theta waves on the resting state EEG supports the existence of a strong link
249 between cognition and the neural processes reflected by theta waves of resting-state EEG.

250 **A physiological hypothesis linking cognitive impairment and increased theta wave** 251 **activity: local sleep**

252 Sleep and wakefulness are not entities separated by clearly defined boundaries: the transition
253 from one to the other does not occur in an On/Off mode but in various ways both spatially and
254 temporally^{137, 138}.

255 In rats, an increase in theta waves reflects the need for sleep, just as in humans¹³⁹. Local sleep
256 islands have been identified in the cortex of this animal when it is fully awake but sleep-
257 deprived (transient neuronal OFF periods). These islands result in a local increase in theta
258 waves¹⁴⁰ and are accompanied by a decrease in cognitive performance.

259 In humans, the coexistence of awake and sleeping areas within the same cerebral lobe has
260 been demonstrated by stereo-EEG¹³⁷.

261 A study in healthy sleep-deprived subjects showed the appearance of theta waves on EEG,
262 temporally and spatially linked to specific tasks; these theta waves are also associated with
263 decreased performance and changes in functional MRI¹⁴¹. Similar results were found in
264 another study¹⁴². Furthermore, specific theta waves predictive of errors (large-amplitude theta
265 bursts) have been found on the EEG of healthy sleep-deprived subjects¹⁴³.

266 The occurrence of error-predictive theta waves associated with "neuronal lapses" has been
267 found in stereo-EEG in sleep-deprived subjects, confirming the existence of such a neuronal
268 mechanism in humans¹⁴⁴.

269 The existence of local sleep islands, reflected on the resting-state EEG by an increase in theta
270 waves, thus appears to be a possible physiological mechanism to link sleep disorders and
271 cognitive disorders encountered in schizophrenic patients.

272 **Discussion:**

273 The increased prominence of slow waves (delta and theta) on resting-state EEG is not specific
274 to schizophrenia spectrum disorders. It is found in numerous psychiatric, neurodevelopmental,
275 and neurodegenerative disorders¹⁴⁵, although it is not possible to assert that the same
276 physiological mechanism is involved in all these conditions. Moreover, it wasn't always found
277 initially. observed in schizophrenia spectrum disorders—in macroscale characteristics¹⁴⁶,
278 which raises the question of the existence of patient subgroups and recording techniques.

279 The hypothesis of local sleep as a link between certain disorders of the schizophrenic
280 spectrum and the increase in the importance of theta waves on resting-state EEG remains a
281 hypothesis but this link has been demonstrated in patients suffering from ADHD¹⁴⁷.

282 Currently, there are no spectral EEG data available for patients with schizophrenia spectrum
283 disorders treated with sertraline, methylphenidate or xanomeline. Only such data could
284 confirm the link between the improvement of cognitive impairment and the reduction in theta
285 waves on resting-state EEG.

286 The three models reviewed here share physiological traits relevant to the study of
287 schizophrenia but also differ in part, which on the one hand may limit their relevance but on
288 the other hand allows for the individualization of their specific contribution.

289 Sleep deprivation is not, of course, identical to schizophrenia. It differs in its rapid
290 reversibility but nevertheless remains a relevant model because it reproduces the same
291 temporal sequence of onset of symptoms as schizophrenia: cognitive impairment, then mood
292 disturbances, and finally hallucinations and delusions⁹¹. It therefore reproduces the genesis of
293 psychosis in time-lapse – but it can no longer be studied over long periods for obvious ethical
294 reasons.

295 22q11 duplication syndrome helps clarify the role of haplotypy in the genes involved in
296 22q11 deletions. While psychiatric disorders are also very common in 22q11 duplication
297 syndrome, those on the schizophrenic spectrum are exceptional^{148, 149}. Sleep disturbances are
298 as significant in 22q11 duplication syndrome as in 22q11 deletion syndrome, but psychotic
299 symptoms are less pronounced¹⁵⁰, as are cognitive¹⁵¹ and social difficulties¹⁵². The number of
300 copies of the genes involved in section 22q11 thus appears to play a role in both the severity
301 of cognitive impairment and the development of psychotic symptoms, suggesting both a
302 continuum in cognitive impairment and a threshold effect of this impairment on the onset of
303 debilitating symptoms.

304 Numerous findings support the existence of a continuum between normal and pathological
305 conditions¹⁵³. For example, in 22q11 deletion syndrome, subclinical symptoms, as well as
306 cognitive impairments⁷⁸, affect significantly more individuals than those diagnosed with
307 schizophrenia or autism spectrum disorder¹⁵⁴. Hallucinations and delusions are also not
308 uncommon in the general population^{155, 156, 157, 158}. The link between cognitive impairments
309 and childhood trauma has been found in both psychotic patients and the general population⁵⁰.
310 Cognitive biases are present in everyone, including physicians¹⁵⁹, but not with the same
311 intensity¹⁶⁰.

312 The existence of a threshold effect on a continuum of cognitive and symptomatic disorders
313 explains why some individuals transition into a pathological state while others exhibit
314 psychotic symptoms (hallucinations, delusions) without this affecting their social integration.
315 These thresholds vary according to the individuals' cultural context; hallucinations are
316 systematically considered pathological in Western societies, while many delusional
317 interpretations of reality are more readily accepted.

318 The hypothesis of a continuum with thresholds also makes it possible to account for the
319 reversibility of certain psychoses, whether it concerns people diagnosed as schizophrenic but
320 whose exceptional destiny illustrates the possibility of a reversibility of the disorders¹⁶¹, or
321 psychoses whose prognosis is better than that of disorders on the schizophrenia spectrum such
322 as brief psychotic disorder, epileptic psychoses, puerperal psychoses, drug-induced
323 psychoses (iatrogenic or toxic), NMDAR encephalitis.

324 The possibility of complete reversibility of these disorders underscores the limitations of
325 current treatment for schizophrenia spectrum disorders. Neuroleptics are effective in only
326 two-thirds of patients, and primarily on positive symptoms. Their efficacy compared to
327 placebo has been steadily declining over the decades¹⁶². Clozapine, the standard active
328 substance in cases of treatment resistance, performs little better than olanzapine or
329 risperidone¹⁶³. Continuous use of neuroleptic medication does not prevent the frequent
330 occurrence of relapses¹⁶⁴. Moreover, what is considered a good response to treatment is a
331 relatively modest reduction in symptoms assessed using intermediate criteria that do not
332 accurately reflect the patients' functional prognosis¹⁶⁵. All of this certainly explains, in part,
333 the frequency with which patients discontinue treatment¹⁶⁶.

334 It is interesting to note that the positive results obtained with sertraline^{127, 128, 129, 130, 131, 132}
335 were achieved by combining it with a reduced dose of olanzapine, ziprasidone, paliperidone

336 or risperidone because all neuroleptics cause a slowing of the EEG¹⁶⁷. This slowing is
337 particularly significant for clozapine, whose detrimental effect on cognition has been
338 demonstrated¹⁶⁸.

339 Similarly, a recent meta-analysis on the effectiveness of high-frequency rTMS on negative
340 symptoms showed that it was significantly more effective with low doses of neuroleptics than
341 with high doses¹⁶⁹.

342 **Limitations:**

343 There are several limitations regarding the action of the pharmacological agents cited to
344 highlight the strength of the correlation between the decrease in theta wave activity on
345 resting-state EEG and an improvement in symptoms and cognition: studies on 5HT2a receptor
346 agonists, as well as those on xanomelin, are conducted on animals, not humans; studies
347 showing a decrease in resting theta wave activity with psychostimulants primarily involve
348 patients with ADHD, while those showing the same effect with sertraline involve patients
349 with major depression. Nevertheless, there is nothing to prevent conducting such studies in
350 patients with schizophrenia spectrum disorders to provide evidence of this effect in this
351 population.

352 **Conclusion:**

353 The hypothesis of the intrusion of local sleep islands into brain function remains a hypothesis,
354 but the clinical effect of the active substances causing a decrease in theta waves of the resting-
355 state EEG is partially demonstrated and is fully demonstrable through clinical trials on
356 patients suffering from schizophrenic spectrum disorders.

357 If confirmed, this effect would open new avenues for treatment of schizophrenia spectrum
358 disorders, offering less bleak prospects. The safety of psychostimulants in this context has
359 already been demonstrated¹²², ¹²³ that of low doses of psychedelics has been positively
360 reassessed¹⁷⁰, and that of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors has long been established.

361 Reducing the dosage of neuroleptics used by combining them with active substances that
362 normalize the increase in the importance of theta waves in the resting-state EEG could
363 contribute to the improvement of symptoms and cognitive disorders, and make patients more
364 easily accessible to metacognition¹⁷¹ and regaining control of their lives.

365

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